

ISic2885

I.Sicily inscription 2885

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

volcanic (local, from Fuardo)

Object

stele

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lipara

Place of origin (modern)

Lipari

Provenance

Contr. Diana, sporadic find

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Lipari, Museo Archeologico

Regionale Eoliano "Luigi Bernabò Brea", inventory 15179

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI334884

1. Dis M [anibus]

2. □ SCL#⁷ [— — —]

3. #⁷#⁷ [— — — —]

4. ID I [— — — —]

5.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645278

PHI 334884

Bibliography

Bernabò Brea, L., Cavalier, M., Campagna, L. 2003. Meligunìs Lipára. XII. Le iscrizioni lapidarie greche e latine delle isole eolie. Palermo. At 776

Bernabò Brea, L., Cavalier, M. 1994. Meligunis Lipara VII. Lipari. Contrada Diana. Scavo XXXVI in proprietà Zagami (1975-1984). Palermo. At no.112 pl.136

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